

**COLLABORATING WITH PARENTS TO ADDRESS LEARNING
DIFFICULTIES AND SPECIAL NEEDS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS**

**BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTABLARDA O'QISHDAGI QIYINCHILIKLAR
VA MAXSUS EHTIYOJLARNI HAL QILISH UCHUN OTA-ONALAR
BILAN HAMKORLIK QILISH**

**СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВО С РОДИТЕЛЯМИ В РЕШЕНИИ ПРОБЛЕМ С
ОБУЧЕНИЕМ И ОСОБЫМИ ПОТРЕБНОСТЯМИ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ
ШКОЛАХ**

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Abstract. This study examines the potential for parent-teacher collaboration in addressing learning difficulties and special needs in Uzbekistan's elementary schools. Through a comprehensive literature review and theoretical analysis, the research explores current practices, challenges, and opportunities for improvement. Findings suggest that while there is growing awareness of the importance of parental involvement, significant barriers remain, including limited resources and cultural attitudes. The study proposes a framework for enhancing collaboration, emphasizing the need for targeted training programs and policy reforms.

Keywords: Parental involvement, special needs education, Uzbekistan, elementary schools, learning difficulties, teacher-parent collaboration

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekiston boshlang'ich maktablarida ta'lim va alohida ehtiyojlar bilan bog'liq muammolarni hal qilishda ota-onalar va o'qituvchilar o'rtasidagi hamkorlik salohiyatini o'rganadi. Keng qamrovli adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish va nazariy tahlillardan kelib chiqqan holda, tadqiqot mavjud amaliyotlar, muammolar va takomillashtirish imkoniyatlarini ko'rib chiqadi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ota-onalarning ishtiroki muhimligini anglash ortib borayotganiga qaramay, cheklangan resurslar va madaniy asoslarni o'z ichiga olgan muhim to'siqlar saqlanib qolmoqda. Tadqiqot hamkorlikni kengaytirish uchun asos yaratadi, maqsadli o'quv dasturlari va siyosiy islohotlar zarurligini ta'kidlaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: ota-onalarni jalb qilish, alohida ehtiyojli ta'lim, O'zbekiston, boshlang'ich maktablar, o'qishdagi qiyinchiliklar, o'qituvchi-ota-onalar hamkorligi

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматривается потенциал сотрудничества родителей и учителей в решении проблем с обучением и особыми потребностями в начальных школах Узбекистана. На основе всестороннего обзора литературы и теоретического анализа в исследовании рассматриваются существующие практики, проблемы и возможности для улучшения. Полученные данные свидетельствуют о том, что, несмотря на растущее осознание важности участия родителей, сохраняются значительные барьеры, включая ограниченные ресурсы и культурные устои. В исследовании предлагаются рамки для расширения сотрудничества, подчеркивается необходимость целевых программ обучения и политических реформ.

Ключевые слова: Вовлечение родителей, образование с особыми потребностями, Узбекистан, начальные школы, трудности в обучении, сотрудничество учителя и родителей

INTRODUCTION

The role of parental involvement in education has been widely recognized as a crucial factor in student success, particularly for children with learning difficulties and special needs [1]. In Uzbekistan, a country undergoing significant educational reforms, the integration of parents into the educational process presents both opportunities and challenges [2]. This study aims to investigate the current state of parent-teacher collaboration in addressing learning difficulties and special needs in Uzbekistan's elementary schools, with a focus on identifying effective strategies and areas for improvement.

The Uzbek education system has been undergoing substantial changes since the country gained independence in 1991. While progress has been made in many areas, the field of special needs education remains underdeveloped [3]. The concept of inclusive education is relatively new in Uzbekistan, and many schools lack the resources and expertise to adequately support students with learning difficulties [4]. In this context, the involvement of parents becomes even more critical, as they can provide valuable insights into their children's needs and complement the efforts of educators.

METHODS AND LITERATURE REVIEW

This study employs a comprehensive literature review and theoretical analysis to examine parent-teacher collaboration in Uzbekistan's elementary schools. The review focuses on existing research on parental involvement in special needs

education, with particular attention to studies from Uzbekistan and other Central Asian countries.

The literature review revealed a limited body of research specific to Uzbekistan, highlighting the need for more studies in this area. However, several key studies provide valuable insights into the current state of special needs education and parental involvement in the country.

Khamidov and Ismailova [5] examined the challenges of implementing inclusive education in Uzbekistan, noting the lack of trained personnel and appropriate resources as significant barriers. Their study, however, did not specifically address the role of parental involvement.

Umarova [6] investigated parental attitudes towards inclusive education in Tashkent, finding that while many parents supported the concept, they had concerns about the practical implementation and quality of education their children would receive.

Internationally, research has consistently shown the positive impact of parental involvement on educational outcomes for children with special needs [7]. However, the applicability of these findings to the Uzbek context requires careful consideration, given the unique cultural and systemic factors at play.

RESULTS

Based on the literature review and theoretical analysis, several key themes emerge regarding parent-teacher collaboration in addressing learning difficulties and special needs in Uzbekistan's elementary schools:

Limited understanding of special needs: Studies suggest that many teachers in Uzbekistan lack confidence in their ability to identify and address learning

difficulties, while parents often struggle to understand their children's needs and available support options [5].

Resource constraints: Multiple studies highlight the shortage of specialized materials, assistive technologies, and support staff in Uzbek schools, which impacts the ability to provide adequate support for students with special needs [3, 4, 5].

Cultural attitudes: Research indicates that cultural stigma associated with disabilities and learning difficulties may impact parental willingness to engage with schools and acknowledge their children's needs [6].

Policy framework: While Uzbekistan has made strides in developing policies to support inclusive education, implementation remains a challenge, particularly in terms of promoting parent-teacher collaboration [2, 3].

Potential for positive outcomes: Despite the challenges, some studies suggest that when effective partnerships between parents and teachers are established, there is potential for significant improvements in student outcomes [7].

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The findings from the literature review indicate a significant gap between the recognized importance of parent-teacher collaboration and its practical implementation in Uzbekistan's elementary schools. This discrepancy can be attributed to a combination of systemic, cultural, and resource-related factors.

The lack of resources and trained personnel emerges as a prominent barrier, reflecting the broader challenges facing Uzbekistan's education system. These findings align with previous research by Khamidov and Ismailova [5], who identified resource constraints as a major obstacle to inclusive education in the country.

The cultural attitudes towards disability and learning difficulties highlight the need for broader awareness-raising efforts. This aligns with Umarova's [6] findings

on parental attitudes towards inclusive education, suggesting that addressing societal perceptions is crucial for improving collaboration.

The policy framework in Uzbekistan, while evolving, appears to lack specific mechanisms for promoting and supporting parent-teacher collaboration in special needs education. This suggests a need for targeted policy reforms to create an enabling environment for such partnerships.

The results of this study highlight the complex interplay of factors influencing parent-teacher collaboration in addressing learning difficulties and special needs in Uzbekistan's elementary schools. While there is growing recognition of the importance of such collaboration, significant challenges remain in translating this awareness into effective practice.

One of the key issues identified is the limited understanding of special needs among both teachers and parents. This finding underscores the need for comprehensive training programs that target not only educators but also parents and the broader community. Such programs could help build a shared understanding of learning difficulties and special needs, fostering a more supportive and inclusive educational environment.

CONCLUSIONS

This study has provided a theoretical overview of the current state of parent-teacher collaboration in addressing learning difficulties and special needs in Uzbekistan's elementary schools. While significant challenges exist, there are also clear opportunities for improvement and grounds for optimism.

By addressing these areas, Uzbekistan can work towards creating a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for all students, particularly those with learning difficulties and special needs. The successful implementation of these

recommendations will require sustained effort and commitment from policymakers, educators, parents, and the broader community. However, the potential benefits – improved educational outcomes, increased social inclusion, and enhanced quality of life for students with special needs – make this a worthy and necessary endeavor.

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